

Federated Intrusion Detection for Smart Vehicles

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Abstract—Cybersecurity threats are increasingly endangering networked systems consisting of multiple nodes, such as Internet of Things (IoT) systems, Supply Chains and Smart Cars, mainly due to the emergence of new types of unknown (zero-day) attacks and the growth of vulnerable IoT devices. While earlier research has shown that Machine Learning (ML)-based Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs) can enhance security, the efficacy and practicality of ML-based IDSs that require large labeled training data, are often limited by their ability to only access private data. This challenge becomes more pronounced in the case of a distributed system, where each node must ensure the confidentiality of local data but faces attacks that are similar to those faced by other nodes in the system. Thus, this paper proposes a novel Decentralized and Asynchronous IDS based on Online Self-Supervised Federated Learning called the iDAF system that improves overall security by providing collaborative data confidentiality-preserving learning among all nodes. iDAF enables self-supervised learning without human intervention, eliminates the need for large labeled data, and avoids long-lasting local training sessions. The performance of iDAF is evaluated to detect DoS and DDoS attacks in two different scenarios of Collaborating IoT Networks and Connected Smart Cars using three online datasets and compared with five benchmark methods. The results show that iDAF delivers outstanding performance, providing high intrusion detection accuracy with an acceptable computation time and considerably low communication overhead. We anticipate that the iDAF system can be a key enabler in developing fully online and collaborative learning security tools for distributed networked systems.

Index Terms—Federated Learning, Intrusion Detection, Cybersecurity, Internet of Things (IoT), DoS attacks, DDoS attacks, Botnets, Connected Vehicles

I. INTRODUCTION

The massive increase in the number and variety of connected devices to over 20 Billion in 2025 has substantially increased the number and risk of cyberattacks [1], [2]. Among these, Denial of Service (DoS) and Distributed DoS (DDoS) are very common, and they overload their victim devices with a large flow of communication traffic over a short time [3], causing operational slowdowns, delays, and system shutdowns. DDoS attacks typically exploit simple Internet of Things (IoT) devices that are compromised, and which generate further attacks. Thus, Intrusion Detection Systems (IDSs) that can detect cyberattacks, and in particular DoS and DDoS attacks, are needed as an essential component of cybersecurity. Machine Learning (ML) is often used to design IDSs due to the large variability of attack traffic characteristics, and learn from large datasets that contain real attacks and

benign communication traffic for vehicles [4], where distinct vehicles operate together in a data-driven environment [5], [6], with each vehicle receives distinct network traffic. If such flows are pooled, each vehicle can learn from the data and experience of other vehicles. However, different manufacturers of vehicles may use data in different formats and may be unable to share proprietary data due to technical or commercial constraints. Similarly, sharing the locations and occupancies of different vehicles can violate the privacy of the passengers. Federated Learning (FL) [7] can facilitate the sharing of data if it is synthesized in the form of neural network weights or anonymized higher-level information, without the need to share the local traffic streams (or their statistics) received by different vehicles.

Therefore, this paper proposes a novel Federated IDS called Intrusion Detection Algorithm with Federation (iDAF) for Online Self-Supervised Federated Learning for Connected Vehicles, based on independently collaborating mobile networked nodes, that uses the same local self-supervised on-line ML algorithm with the same number of neurons and neuronal network structure. Each local ML algorithm learns from its own local data in a self-supervised manner, and shares its weights *asynchronously* with other collaborating nodes after a pre-determined number of learning updates. Each node then fuses the weights it receives with its own weights, in a manner which gives greater importance to those other nodes' weights which are numerically closer to its own. The core single-node IDS that we use is from our earlier work [8], but iDAF contrasts with much of the existing work on FL : (1) It is asynchronous, which allows nodes to progress at their own pace, accelerating the individual speed of computation without nodes being slowed down by the slowest node. (2) iDAF uses Proximity-based Weight Averaging so that each vehicle learns more from others whose experience is similar to its own, contrary to uniform approaches such as weight averaging. As a result, we observe that iDAF is faster and more accurate than other FL baseline methods.

In the rest of this paper, Section I-A reviews recent related work on FL for cybersecurity, Section II details the iDAF algorithm that is introduced in this paper and its local learning with asynchronous distributed FL updates. Section III evaluates and compares iDAF with other benchmark methods and Section IV briefly presents conclusions and suggests some future research.

A. Related Research

Since the statistical characteristics of DoS and DDoS traffic are hard to identify [9], Machine Learning (ML) has been used to design IDSs to achieve high accuracy and low false alarm rates [10], [11], with the ability to detect different

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types of attacks with the same IDS [12], [13]. FL can be centralized, by updating the distinct local learning algorithms in a central server and creating a common model which is shared with all distinct entities, or it may be decentralized with distinct collaborating entities that exchange their local updates with each other. In recent work on the centralized approach in [14], experiments were carried out with DDoS and False Data Injection attacks against vehicular systems. In [15], Federated Deep Belief Network-based IDS for intrusion detection used the Aegean Wi-Fi Intrusion Dataset (AWID). In [16], centralized FL malware detection was developed for the industrial IoT using a Generative Adversarial Network (GANs), and in [17] a multi-step prediction method was used for DDoS attacks, with Hidden Markov Models and a centralized FL architecture using Reinforcement Learning. Also, in [18], an architecture is proposed for DDoS attack mitigation with a centralized approach to shorten the time needed to mitigate attacks.

To protect against gradient attacks, a decentralized FL approach is suggested in [19], that averages the contributions of peers to simplify the transmission, aggregation, and synchronization of each entity's data, while in [20] blockchain-based FL focused on detecting poisoning attacks using a decentralized architecture. Also, in [21] a decentralized federated learning was employed to identify anomalies in network traffic generated by IoT devices. The work in [22] addresses the single point of failure problem in the centralized FL approach and reviews intrusion detection systems based on decentralized FL and distributed ledger techniques for the IoT. Also, in [23] an FL approach for intrusion detection based on blockchain technology was proposed with various learning algorithms such as Scaled Conjugate Gradient, Bayesian Regularization, and Levenberg-Marquardt, to train the ML model, and apply the resulting neural weights to the FL model. In [24], a lightweight, decentralized deep learning architecture, called FED-IDS, was introduced to detect cyberattacks in heterogeneous Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS). Although the performance obtained by this architecture is promising, the proposed architecture does not meet the real-time requirement of ITS as it is not computationally efficient. In a recent work [25], authors presented a detection model emphasizing a mesh satellite network architecture and asynchronous FL to identify cyberattacks in autonomous vehicles. However, a notable gap in their model lies in the lack of trust in the connected nodes, prompting the need for blockchain integration.

II. INTRUSION DETECTION WITH FEDERATION: IDAF

We first present the base IDS used at each node, both as part of the proposed iDAF system and as the local Benchmark Decision-Maker. At each node n , it operates in successive time windows of T_n seconds. As shown in Figure 1, at the l -th successive window, the IDS, which consists of the Deep Random Neural Network (DRNN) [26], first used for attack detection in [8], is an extension of the Random Neural Network [27]. It has a square feedforward structure of three fully connected layers with three input and intermediate

clusters of neurons, and an output layer composed of linear neurons. It uses the Statistical Whisker-based Benign Classifier (SWBC) to provide a binary intrusion decision y_n^l in response to the input vector x_n^l . Three statistics at the input to the IDS measure the temporal characteristics of the incoming network traffic in the l -th window at node n : the average packet length μ_n^l , the number of arriving packets per second λ_n^l , and the number of bytes per second ρ_n^l , represented by the vector $x_n^l = [\mu_n^l, \lambda_n^l, \rho_n^l]$. Let p_n^t be a packet that is generated in node n at time instance t and has a size of $|p_n^t|$ in bytes, and P_n^l denote the set of such packets generated within the time window l :

$$P_n^l = \{p_n^t : (l-1)T_n \leq t < lT_n\}, \text{ hence :}$$

$$\mu_n^l = \frac{\sum_{p \in P_n^l} |p|}{|P_n^l|}, \lambda_n^l = \frac{|P_n^l|}{T_n}, \rho_n^l = \frac{\sum_{p \in P_n^l} |p|}{T_n},$$

where the latter three metrics are normalized to take values in the range $[0, 1]$. We denote by X_n^l the vector of these input values at node n , that is computed from the traffic data after window l .

Fig. 1. Structure of the IDS (I_n^l) utilized by every node n in iDAF.

We note that an initial or final portion of attack datasets is, in general, comprised of benign traffic, as with the well-known Mirai Botnet data set [28], which starts with a long sequence of benign traffic before the Botnet starts. Therefore, we select a sequence of M benign packets, and divide it into L equal-sized subsequences of time windows each of length T_n , yielding the set of input values denoted by $\{x_{n,i}^l : i = 1, 2, 3, l = 1, \dots, L\}$, and the corresponding vectors $X(n)^1, \dots, X(n)^L$.

At the l -th window, the input vector X_n^l applied to the IDS, results in the output vector \hat{X}_n^l :

$$\hat{X}(n)^l = \eta(\eta(X(n)^l W(n)_1) W(n)_2), \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{X}(n)^l$ is the output vector of the DRNN, whose elements are $\hat{x}(n)_i^l, i = 1, 2, 3$, $W(n)_1, W(n)_2$ are the connection matrices from from layer 1 to layer 2, and from layer 2 to layer 3, respectively, and $\eta(\cdot)$ is the transfer function of the DRNN. These weight matrices are learned with the algorithm developed in [29] and used in [8]:

$$W(n)^l \leftarrow \arg \min_{W(n)_1^{l-1}, W(n)_2^{l-1} \geq 0} \{ \|W(n)^{l-1}\|_{L_1} + \|X_n^l - \eta(\eta(X_n^l W(n)_1^{l-1}) W(n)_2^{l-1})\|_{L_2} \}, \quad (2)$$

where $W(n)^{l-1}$ is the 6×6 block-diagonal matrix composed of $W(n)_1^{l-1}, W(n)_2^{l-1}$, while L_1, L_2 refer to the norms, and

η is the DRNN vector transfer function. The minimization can be computed using the Fast Iterative Shrinkage-Thresholding Algorithm [30]. A more gradual, but more computationally intensive, form of the learning algorithm can also be used:

$$W^*(n)^l \leftarrow (1 - \epsilon)W^*(n)^{l-1} + \epsilon \arg \min_{W^*(n)_1^{l-1}, W^*(n)_2^{l-1} \geq 0} [\|X_n^l - \eta(\eta(X_n^l W^*(n)_1^{l-1}) W^*(n)_2^{l-1})\|_{L_2} + \|W^*(n)^{l-1}\|_{L_1}],$$

with small values of ϵ , but this will not be discussed any further in this paper. Now let $\{w_{n,i}^l\}$ be the *statistical whisker value* of $\{x_{n,i}^1, \dots, x_{n,i}^L\}$, for $i = 1, 2, 3$, and define

$$\zeta_n^l = \sum_{i=1}^3 \mathbf{1}(|x_{n,i}^l - \hat{x}_{n,i}^l| > \frac{3}{2}w_{n,i}^l), \mathbf{y}_n^l = \mathbf{1}(|\zeta_n^l| > \theta_n) > \mathbf{0},$$

where y_n^l is the binary decision value for detection an attack at the l -th window of the n -th node, based on a ‘‘threshold’’ θ_n , so that:

- If $y_n^{l-1} = 1$, the decision is that the traffic at node n in window l is malicious, and
- Otherwise, the decision is that it is benign.

where:

- We first obtain the weight matrix $W(n)$ using the algorithm (2).
- We then compute the corresponding output vector sequence $\hat{X}(n)^1, \dots, \hat{X}(n)^L$ using (1), and therefore also $\{\hat{x}_{n,i}^l : i = 1, 2, 3, l = 1, \dots, L\}$,
- Then we obtain $\zeta_n^l, l = 1, \dots, L$, and
- We set $\theta_n = Avg(\zeta_n) + 2\sqrt{Var(\zeta_n)}$.

A. iDAF Fuses Weights with Collaborating Nodes

The iDAF federated structure is shown in Figure 2, where node n operates asynchronously with respect to other nodes, and proceeds to fuse its weights with the weights of other nodes as soon as it has received the most recent value of the weights from more than half, i.e. more than $N/2$ of the other nodes. Denote by $W(m)_1, W(m)_2$ the weights that n has received from another node m , and let R be the set of indices of the nodes from which it has received updates. The iDAF node update process is as follows:

- The $n - th$ node selects the node whose h -layer weights are closest to its own in the same layer, to merge its h -layer weights:

$$m(n)_h^* = \arg \min_{m \in R} \|W(m)_h - W(n)_h\|_{L_1}. \quad (3)$$

- The merger is carried out for the $h - level$ weight matrix of node n in the following manner:

$$W(n)_h \leftarrow (1 - c)W(m(n)_h^*)_h + cW(n)_h, \quad (4)$$

where $1 \geq c \geq 0.5$. Note that we do not require that $m(n)_h^* = m(n)_{h'}^*$, for $h \neq h'$.

- In addition, the threshold is also merged.

- For each whisker $w_{n,i}^l$ of SWBC in I_n^l , the node m_i^* that has the whisker value closest to $w_{n,i}^l$ is obtained:

$$m_i^* = \arg \min_{m \in C_n^l} \left(|w_{n,i}^l - w_{m,i}^l| \right), \quad (5)$$

and then $w_{n,i}^l$ is updated as

$$w_{n,i}^l \leftarrow c w_{n,i}^l + (1 - c) w_{m_i^*,i}^l. \quad (6)$$

- The node m_θ^* that has the threshold value closest to θ_n^l is obtained:

$$m_\theta^* = \arg \min_{m \in C_n^l} \left(|\theta_n^l - \theta_m^l| \right), \quad (7)$$

and θ_n^l becomes:

$$\theta_n^l \leftarrow c \theta_n^l + (1 - c) \theta_{m_\theta^*}^l. \quad (8)$$

Fig. 2. Schematic system representation of iDAF.

B. Fusion Rules for Comparison

The Fusion Rules that are tested and compared are the following: - The ‘‘Non-Federated Approach’’, where each local IDS learns from local data, but does not fuse weights with other nodes.

- ‘‘Average over All Collaborating Nodes’’ or ‘‘Average’’ simply updates the neural weights of $IDAF - n$ by averaging them with the those of the other $N - 1$ nodes, hence:

$$W(n)_h \leftarrow \frac{1}{N} \sum_{m \in N} W(m)_h, \quad (9)$$

The whisker and threshold parameters are similarly updated:

$$w_{n,i}^l \leftarrow \frac{1}{N} \sum_{m \in N} w_{m,i}^l \quad \forall i, \quad \theta_n^l \leftarrow \frac{1}{N} \sum_{m \in N} \theta_m^l, \quad (10)$$

and the parameters of all nodes remain unchanged until the next learning window.

- ‘‘Average with Closest Node (ACN)’’ updates the weights by averaging with the node $m_i(n)$ whose parameters are closest:

$$m_i(n) = \arg \min_{m \in \mathcal{N} \setminus n} \left[\sum_{h=1}^H \left\| W(n)_h^l - W(m)_h^l \right\|_1 + \sum_{i=1}^3 \left| w_{n,i}^l - w_{m,i}^l \right| + \left| \theta_n^l - \theta_m^l \right| \right].$$

Then the weights are updated for each n :

$$W(n)_h^l \leftarrow \frac{W(n)_h^l + W(m^*)_h^l}{2}, \quad \forall h \quad (11)$$

$$w_{n,i}^l \leftarrow \frac{w_{n,i}^l + w_{m^*,i}^l}{2}, \quad \forall i \quad \theta_n^l \leftarrow \frac{\theta_n^l + \theta_{m^*}^l}{2}.$$

- The ‘‘Average with Closest Node per Layer (ACN-L)’’ approach, updates each weight of $iDAF - n$ for each layer, whisker and threshold by individually taking the average with the corresponding parameter of the node that is closest with regard to that parameter. For each layer h , the connection weights are updated using m_h^* :

$$W(n)_h^l \leftarrow \frac{W(n)_h^l + W(m_h^*)_h^l}{2}, \quad (12)$$

where

$$m_h^* = \arg \min_{m \in \mathcal{N} \setminus n} \left(\left\| W(n)_h^l - W(m)_h^l \right\|_2 \right). \quad (13)$$

Then, each whisker $w_{n,i}^l$ of SWBC in I_n^l is updated (6) for a value of m_i^* calculated using (5):

$$w_{n,i}^l \leftarrow \frac{w_{n,i}^l + w_{m_i^*,i}^l}{2}, \quad (14)$$

where

$$m_i^* = \arg \min_{m \in \mathcal{N} \setminus n} \left(\left\| w_{n,i}^l - w_{m,i}^l \right\|_2 \right). \quad (15)$$

The decision threshold θ_n^l is also updated using (7) and (8):

$$\theta_n^l \leftarrow \frac{\theta_n^l + \theta_{m_\theta^*}^l}{2}, \quad \text{and } m_\theta^* = \arg \min_{m \in \mathcal{N} \setminus n} \left(\left\| \theta_n^l - \theta_m^l \right\|_2 \right). \quad (16)$$

- The ‘‘Synchronous Federated’’ algorithm is also used as a comparison since it achieves very accurate detection with federated updates in each time window [31], based on the parameters locally learned at each node.

III. RESULTS

We now discuss the performance of $iDAF$ for DoS/DDoS attacks against the CAN-bus of smart cars, in comparison with the other methods that were outlined, for a system with $N = 3$ nodes where the first node uses the ‘‘Mirai Botnet’’ dataset [32], the second uses the ‘‘DoS HTTP’’ benign dataset, and the third uses the ‘‘DDoS HTTP’’ attack dataset, the latter two being presented in [33]. Evaluation are implemented are on a server with 16 GB of RAM and an M1 Pro 8-core 3.2 GHz processor with threading and the concurrent operation of all

three $iDAF$ nodes. The evaluation of $iDAF$ uses $c = 0.75$, and the learning algorithm updates local parameters if 5 or more of the last 10 windows are classified as benign, to carry out online associative learning only with benign traffic. Since a cold-start with benign traffic is needed, we have extracted a benign sequence from the specific dataset used for each node. The value of T_n is set follows: it is 23 for Mirai, 9 for DoS HTTP, and 8 for DDoS HTTP. Note that all datasets are labelled with the binary ground truth $a(p_n^t)$, for each packet p_n^t that tells us whether each packet is ‘‘benign’’ or ‘‘malicious’’, for comparison with the predictions of the different intrusin detectors.

We evaluate the $iDAF$ system to detect CAN-bus DoS attacks based on the dataset [34] from Eindhoven University of Technology for an Opel Astra and a Renault Clio vehicle that use a CAN-bus prototype. Performance of the different approaches is evaluated with the ‘‘testing.log’’ and ‘‘dosattack.log’’ files from the Opel Astra, the Renault, and the Prototype car. The testing.log file contains only normal CAN-bus data, but the dosattack.log file is composed of clearly labelled normal and attack data, so that each file can be assumed to related to an individual car, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. The scenario of connected smart cars targeted by CAN-bus DoS attacks.

We first compare the computation time used by each method for a single federated update in Table I. We observe that a federated parameter update in $iDAF$ takes approximately 32 ms for connected cars. Furthermore, $iDAF$'s computation time is lat-rger than that of the other methods we consider, namely Average, ACN and ACN-L, but is an order of magnitude smaller than for the Synchronous approach.

TABLE I
AVERAGE COMPUTATION TIME PER WINDOW OF EACH FEDERATED METHOD

Method	Time
$iDAF$	32.1 ms
Synchronous	261.21 ms
Average	57.4 μs
ACN	268.8 μs
ACN-L	299.8 μs

A. Performance of iDAF for Connected Vehicles

Results regarding the use of iDAF for CAN-bus attacks against connected vehicles are shown for six collaborating vehicles. Figure 4 (top) shows that averaging-based methods raise a high number of false alarms, while the performance of iDAF, Synchronous, and No Federated remains good. In Figure 4 (bottom), we observe that iDAF provides slightly more false alarms for Renault and Prototype vehicles, but that it detects malicious traffic with perfect accuracy.

Furthermore, for the Opel DoS dataset, the iDAF, Synchronous and No Federated techniques detect malicious traffic with almost no false alarms. On the other hand, iDAF detects malicious traffic accurately but with a high false alarm rate for Renault and Prototype cars. Note also that the No Federated and Synchronous methods have poor detection performance, achieving TPRs of only 0.1 for the Renault and Prototype vehicles.

Clearly, for critical systems such as the CAN-bus, not being able to identify malicious traffic is far more dangerous than raising too many false alarms.

Fig. 4. Performance comparison of iDAF with benchmark methods (Synchronous, No Federated, Average, ACN, and ACN-L) with respect to TNR (top) and TPR (bottom) for Opel DoS, Renault DoS, and Prototype DoS data.

Figure 5 compares the methods we discuss for vehicles that receive **no attack traffic**, namely Opel Benign, Renault Benign, and Prototype Benign. In this case, we notice that iDAF results in a slightly higher false alarm rate for Renault, but makes almost perfect decisions with very low false alarm rates for the Opel and Prototype cars.

Thus, our experiments with traffic from connected cars appear to indicate that the proposed asynchronous federated parameter update scheme with self-supervised local learning is a useful approach to accurately detect malicious traffic.

Furthermore, Table II shows the total size of all the packets transmitted per vehicle, so that a federated parameter update

Fig. 5. Performance comparison of iDAF with benchmark methods (Synchronous, No Federated, Average, ACN, and ACN-L) with respect to TNR (top) and TPR (bottom) for Opel Benign, Renault Benign, and Prototype Benign data.

may take place, showing that the connected cars using iDAF transmit significantly less data than the Synchronous approach. The Average, ACN, and ACN-L methods need to share less data, but their intrusion detection performance is unacceptably low, as discussed and shown in Section III-A.

TABLE II
TOTAL AMOUNT OF TRAFFIC, IN KILOBYTES (KB), TRANSMITTED BY CONNECTED SMART CARS TO EXCHANGE UP-TO-DATE IDS PARAMETERS, WHICH ARE NOT ENCRYPTED

	Opel		Renault		Prototype	
	DoS	Benign	DoS	Benign	DoS	Benign
iDAF	4.25	4.01	1.18	1.18	8.73	18.17
Sync.	189.04	194.46	34.69	37.29	35.87	37.29
Average	2.36	2.36	2.36	2.36	2.36	2.36
ACN	2.60	2.36	2.60	2.36	2.60	2.36
ACN-L	2.36	2.36	2.83	2.36	2.36	2.36

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We have proposed iDAF, a FL-based asynchronous IDS system that is trained fully online, to allow N nodes to collaboratively learn intrusion detection and increase their detection accuracy while preserving confidentiality of the training data at each node. We have also evaluated its accuracy in detecting DoS and DDoS attacks in several scenarios, and compared the computation time and communication overhead of iDAF against known baseline methods. The results show that iDAF achieves high intrusion detection accuracy by perfectly detecting attacks at almost all nodes with low false alarm rate, and with relatively small learning datasets being collected and processed at each site. We also observe that iDAF operates with a very low, below 0.03%, communication overhead and low computation times when additional data encryption is not used. In addition, for a collaborating IoT network and connected smart cars, respectively, it spends an additional 3.56 ms and 32.1 ms for the federated updates. Finally,

iDAF does not require human intervention and avoids node synchronization. Therefore, the concepts that iDAF embodies may become key constituents of fully online collaborative learning for the security of real-time by connected vehicles.

ACKNOWLEDEMENT

This research was supported by the European Commission Horizon Europe, the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021-2027) DOSS Project under Grant Agreement No: 101120270.

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